

D3.1

version 1.3

Searching for the Common Ground - Exploring the LL sites together using participatory and art-based creative methods

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This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon Europe research and innovation programme under grant agreement No101084220. Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union. Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.

Information about the deliverable			
Project acronym	COEVOLVERS		
Project full title	Coevolutionary approach to unlock the transformative potential of nature-based solutions for more inclusive and resilient communities		
Grant Agreement no	101084220		
Deliverable number	D3.1.		
Deliverable title	Searching for the Common Ground Searching for the Common Ground - Exploring the LL sites together using participatory and art-based creative methods		
Deliverable nature	Report		
Dissemination level	Public		
Work package and Task	Workpackage 3, Task 3.1.		
Contractual delivery date	Month 18		
Actual delivery date	30.4.2024		
Authors	<p>Synthesis: Soini, Katriina; Kull, Michael; Pihlajamäki, Mia; Hiedanpää, Juha</p> <p>Annex 1. Respective LL leaders: Andell, Kia; Pittaway, Tim; Fornara, Ferdinando; Špaček, Martin; Gorriz-Mifsud, Elena; Päll, Lona; Farkas, Gabriella; Pataki, György.</p>		
Reviewers	Timo Maran (University of Tartu), Ferninando Fornara (University of Cagliari)		
Revision History			
Version	Date	Author	Description
Version 1.0	8.4.2024	Soini and Pihlajamäki	First draft sent for reviewers and Living Lab leaders
Version 1.2	16.04.2024	Soini and Pihlajamäki	Revisions based on comments received
Version 1.3	30.04.2024	Soini, Kull, Hiedanpää	Final revision

Statement of originality: This deliverable contains original unpublished work except where clearly indicated otherwise. Acknowledgment of previously published material and of the work of others has been made through appropriate citation, quotation or both.

How to quote this document: Soini et. al., (2024) Exploring the sites together using participatory and art-based creative methods COEVOLVERS D3.1.

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Summary

This report describes a range of events conducted in the COEVOLVERS Living Labs under the Task 3.1. Searching for Common Ground. The aim of the Task was to apply various participatory methods to explore the LL/NBS sites ("places") together with the participants by sharing everyday experiences, feelings, and knowledge associated with the particular place and situation and in this way contribute to community building around the NBS to be explored and co-created.

The activities used various participatory techniques and methods and focused on biophysical environment, meanings of the place and social or political processes associated with the place or the NBS developed. The choice of target group and methods used reflected the aim of the LLs, maturity in collaboration, characteristics of the site, as well as the familiarity to facilitate the participatory methods. Feedback and reflections was collected through the Users' and Facilitators' experience template.

Overall, participants found activities engaging and informative, fostering the sense of community and generating concrete ideas for future collaboration. Practical lessons include time management, accommodating diverse participant backgrounds, and ensuring inclusivity in discussions. From the perspective of the LLs the events helped participants understand how place and its characteristics and NBS design and implementation are interconnected. They also made the stakeholders familiar with the participatory methods used in the Task 3.2. (Mapping the affordances) to explore the meanings of the multispecies living environments and in the Task 3.3. (Understanding the vulnerabilities) to examine the perceptions of vulnerabilities. The events also revealed or confirmed some of the key topics that need a special attention when the governance models are developed further in the WP4. Last but not least, the Searching for common ground events provided material for the design of Toolkit (developed under WP5, Actionable knowledge for transformative NBS) and for communication and dissemination (WP6).

1. Introduction

1.1. Aim of the Task “Searching for the common ground”

The COEVOLVERS-project explores how nature-based solutions (NBS) can contribute to the societal change needed to address ongoing and interconnected environmental and social challenges. The project explores these solutions in seven Living Labs (LLs) across Europe. LLs are real-life sites or “places”, living environments, to explore the design and implementation of NBS in specific socio-political contexts.

This document reports on the activities carried out as part of Task 3.1 “*Searching for the common ground*”. The aim of the Task was to

- apply various participatory methods to explore the LL/NBS sites (“places”) together with the participants by sharing everyday experiences, feelings, and knowledge associated with the particular place and situation and in this way;
- contribute to community building around the NBS to be explored and co-created together through a joint activity connected to the LL site.

Searching for the common ground -events constituted a necessary step in the co-creation activities and started after the kick-off meetings in each LL. From the perspective of the LLs the events helped participants understand how place and its characteristics and NBS design and implementation are interconnected. They also made the stakeholders familiar with the participatory methods that will be used further in the Task 3.2. (Mapping the affordances), where the meanings of the environments are explored more in depth and in the Task 3.3. (Understanding the vulnerabilities), where the perceptions of vulnerabilities are examined. These further activities require not only familiarity with the participatory approaches but also trust among the stakeholders and between the stakeholders and the research teams. The events also revealed or confirmed some of the key topics that need a special attention when the governance models are developed further in the WP4. Last, but not least, the Searching for common ground events provided material for the design of Toolkit (developed under WP5, Actionable knowledge for transformative NBS) and for communication and dissemination (WP6).

1.2. Rationale behind the Task

Places and place-based approaches have been seen as means to navigate in the global change and the societal challenges. Place-perspective for NBS is also essential, as both societal challenges and potential NBS and their design and implementation are always context specific (Albert et al. 2021; Soini et al. 2023). Design of NBS implies an intention to change the place or place-based practice, while people often tend to favour stability in the place relations (Raymond et al. 2023). Implementation of NBS, in turn, may bring along unintended consequences through the co-evolution of human-activities and nature. These are the reasons why ‘place’ is

an important starting point for the LLs and inclusive design and implementation for nature-based solutions. Consequently, the key idea behind the *Searching for common ground* Task is to explore the “place” of the LL together with the LL participants.

Following “place” scholars in geography, architecture, anthropology and social psychology, places are not only (bio)physical entities, but also containers of social and cultural values and meanings (Stedman 2003; Raymond et al. 2021) and results of social and political processes (Sack 1992; Massey 1993, 2005). They are part of the everyday living environment of the stakeholders, including citizens and non-humans, but they may also be objects of planning or valuation (civil servants, policy makers, researchers). Overall stakeholders may hold different perceptions of the values, meanings of the place, as well as of the desired futures of the place.

As (bio)physical and geographical entities places hold certain attributes and ecological processes that provide a setting for human and non-human activities and their interaction (Stedman 2003). Places used to be ‘thick’ with various meanings, as they served for most needs of the humans (Sack 1997) and attached people to the places through family bonds, dwelling and livelihood practices. In the current mobile and hypermodern world, places have become ‘thinner’ serving a single or few purposes by time (Masso et al. 2019). Yet, they are still essential for humans: they are sources of experiences, meanings and social identities; they may gather people together, activate people to preserve or develop the places; they connect human and non-human beings, and are sources of experiences, meanings, and events (Seamon 2018) contributing to their sense of place (Relph 1976; Raymond et al. 2021).

Social and political processes shape the places and how people make sense of them by encompassing various types of human interactions, from relations between family members, neighbourhoods and users of the resources to political power plays and even conflicts between various actors. These processes include formal and informal rules like laws, regulations and norms governing the place-related practices that define how these relations come to be defined, perceived and animated, as well as knowledge processes including how the knowledge is produced, by whom and even, what is considered as a valid knowledge.

The task of the Living Labs was to explore the LLs as “places” through participatory methods. In the following we shortly summarize the key aspects of these activities and then summarize the lessons learnt. All the reports from these events are compiled for the Annex 1. The reports consisted also a section on organisers’ “reflections”, but as these sections contained some sensitive issues they are available only for the internal use. Yet, some key findings from the reflections are reported at the general level in the Chapter 2.3.

2. Searching for common ground - events in COEVOLVERS Living Labs

COEVOLVERS Living Labs (LLs) present a very diverse set of ‘places’ with different geographical scales and development trajectories. Some of the LLs are more mature and participants had earlier collaborated with the COEVOLVERS team (LL Beskydy), some of them have already had activities (LL Alford, LL Pansio-Perno) prior to COEVOLVERS intervention, while some others are new, established during the COEVOLVERS project (LL Cagliari, LL Catalonia, LL Pomáz and LL Tartu). The area of the LL site varies from a hospital garden (Pomáz) to vast and ecologically and socio-economically diverse rural areas in Beskydy. Consequently, each of the LL had to find its own way to “search for a common ground” taking into account also the maturity of the LL, the problem to be solved, maturity of the collaboration, skills of the LL team in participatory methods, and/or characteristics of the site and social environment.

2.1. Participants of the activities

The Living Labs (LLs) have organised themselves as follows: core groups are the operational units, which plan, implement and follow up the co-creation activities together with the researchers. They also make strategic decisions. LL participants are different actors, who represent different stakeholders, like representatives of civil society, local government or public sector (e.g. education, care), business, entrepreneurs and individual citizens (see Table 1.). The composition of the LL participants is dynamic, while the core group represents more stability in order to provide continuity in the activities. The core group planned the events and their target group representing the LLs participants reflecting the needs and aims of the event, and the LL more broadly.

2.2. Type of events & methods used

Each Living Lab core group has developed their own plan of activities (D1.2.) including the Searching for the common ground. Some of the LL have organised only one activity, others already a series of activities. Searching for the common ground can be seen as a continuous effort, starting from the preparatory phase of the project or even earlier in projects prior to COEVOLVERS, like in LL Beskydy, and continuing after delivery of this report.

The LLs were provided a list of potential methods they could use identified in the DoA. Inspiration was also sought from “Arts-based Methods for Transformative Engagement: A Toolkit” (Pearson et al. 2019) and from co-creation methods used in other EU-projects focusing on Nature-based solutions (NBS) (Cihlars et al. 2023). These methods were made available for the LLs. The LLs Labs were given the freedom to choose the methods and design the event(s) as they saw fit considering the target group, place and time of the event(s).

The Living Labs were asked to collect feedback from the participants (see user experience template, Annex 2a and 2b) to support learning how to use these methods with different stakeholder groups. The facilitators were also encouraged to collect feedback through interviews. Selected methods will be attached to the deliverable 1.3 (Methodological review, M24). All of these aspects had implications to the final selection of the most suitable and fruitful participatory methods in a given context.

After the Searching for common ground events, the LLs provided reports including information on the event time and location, participants, programme, participant feedback, and organizers' reflections. These reports are presented in Annex I apart from the organisers' reflections for the reasons explained above. Table 2 below provides a summary of the events.

Most of the activities were linked to the "understanding" phase in the Action Cycle of the COEVOLVERS (D1.2.). LL Turku, Alford and Cagliari also conducted some envisioning activities.

Table 1. Summary of the events organised by the Living Labs.

LL	Objectives	Methods	No. of participants
LL1 Pansio-Perno	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> planning actions to improve the natural and recreational values of local green areas networking through a group work 	Workshop: presentations by a local historian/ resident activist, and the environmental manager of Meyer shipyard; group work to plan actions to improve the natural and recreational values of local green areas.	18
LL2 Alford	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> meanings and values of the park for different stakeholders ways of using the park 	Sharing photos with a brief caption of their favourite place in the park; Workshop (map & stickers to make notes on the map and add their own stories; Slido app to answer: "What word best describes Murray Park woodland for you?"; sharing photos & conversation about the park; discussion based on the presented map layers/zones of the park)	10
LL3 Cagliari	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> mapping the senses, values attributed to the place; co-creating ideas for interventions and activities; 	Explorative walk during which they took photos of points that evoked positive or negative sensations in relation to a potential NBS and describing them in 1-5- words; Mentimeter app to share the words they chose to describe the photos, and to write five words relating to the	21

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> networking through participatory activities 	best and worst place for a potential NBS; group discussion.	
LL4, 1/2 Beskydy	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> benefits of potential NBS 	Workshop: presentations and discussions about NBS challenges and benefits.	16
LL4, 1/2 Beskydy	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> exchange of potential solutions for climate change challenges in the region 	Workshop: presentation on good NBS practices and different aspects of NBSs provided by the organiser and participants on different aspects of NBSs followed by a group discussion.	13
LL5, Catalonia	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> making the various stakeholders more aware of the importance of the sheepfarming for wildlife prevention. 	IVisit to a sheep farm. Presentation with a Q&A session outside with a shepherd in an informal setting while meeting and petting the sheep.	30
LL6, Tartu	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> exploring nonhuman world in the gardens 	Guided sensory walk, where attention was paid to different senses in the perception of the garden, layers of the garden, and what they offered for non-humans. Photo exhibition of the insects living in her garden.	6
LL7, 1/4 Pomáz	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> understanding managers' perspectives, ethical issues, competence and practical issues related to the establishment of the healing garden 	Four meetings with the hospital managers to discuss about COEVOLVERS, the managers' perspectives, ethical, competence and practical issues	3
LL7, 2/4 Pomáz	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> becoming familiar with the garden and its opportunities for the hospital/rehabilitation as well as professionals' needs and proposals 	Site-walks and one-to-one meetings with hospital professionals	4 (one per time)
LL7, 3/4 Pomáz	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> connecting the healing garden/NBS idea with the hospital activities making patients familiar with the healing garden concept 	Two types of meetings with different hospital departments: i) with the professionals and ii) with patients and professionals	Approx. 30

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> getting some reflections, ideas and proposals from the patients 		
LL7, 4/4 Pomáz	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> sharing knowledge about the healing gardens in Hungary and exchanging thoughts (opportunities/barriers) of them 	Open event at the CEU to exchange knowledge and experiences on healing gardens (etc.) in Hungary (presentations and a panel discussion)	Approx. 30

As Table 1 and the LL reports show (Annex I), the LLs chose different approaches and methods for this task, depending on what they considered important for the co-creation process. In LLs Tartu and Beskydy the focus was primarily on the *biophysical world*. Tartu LL explored, together with the participants, the non-human world or 'Umwelt' of the gardens through different methods. LL Beskydy discussed with stakeholders the potential NBS solutions for forestry and other livelihoods in the region and how to adapt to climate change impacts and mitigate the risks it poses to the region. The participants of LL Beskydy had been involved in co-creating a Climate Adaption plan for the region prior to the COEVOLVERS intervention.

LL Pansio-Perno, Cagliari and Alford focused mostly on *different values and meanings* of the place, as well as on possibilities of using the environment in a way that it would benefit both humans and nature and with a variety of participatory methods. In LL Pansio-Perno these values were explored by identifying potential activities to support land-use planning, considering the needs of both humans and nature. In Cagliari the participants' thinking and creativity was first fed with explorative walk. Experiences were shared via the Mentimeter app and in joint discussion. LL Alford used multiple visual methods to explore what people value in the Murray Park and how they use the park. Based on the discussions, all three LLs envisioned some possible actions and future activities conducted within the LLs.

The main focus in LLs Pomáz and Catalonia was on the social and political context and processes within the LLs and around the NBS. In LL Pomáz the target was to find a common and safe space for working with the personel of the institution and its patients. The LL members jointly explored the opportunities and challenges through intensive dialogue involving different stakeholders. Healing gardens associated with hospitals are not commonly known in Hungary. During the process, stakeholders became more knowledgeable about healing garden practice and a platform for collaboration was created. In LL Catalonia the aim was to increase the understanding about shepherding in wildfire prevention and familiarise citizens, both adults and children, with the livelihood of shepherds and their animals through a visit in a park and meeting a shepherd.

From theory point view, all the LLs were mapping relations: relations between stakeholders participating in co-creation and between humans and non-humans. Participants were also able to explore their own values, feelings and emotions towards other interests and the environment. Obviously, the main outcome of these activities was strengthening the basis for the further collaboration by becoming more familiar with the site and other participants. In some LL, the events helped identify critical aspects to be taken into account when planning future activities, as well as design and implementation of the NBS. For example, the issue of access to the water front (LL Pansio-Perno); opportunities of using multiple visual working methods (LL Alford); the importance of networking groups of potential users interested in the park, and responding to their wishes and ideas for future development (LL Cagliari); sharing the knowledge and information and build formal and informal collaboration between the participants regarding NBS (LL Beskydy); recognition of shepherd's work in a fire preventions (LL Catalonia); importance of changing perspective in gardening from humans to non-humans (LL Tartu); finding ways to work with an organisation with complex administrative structure (LL Pomáz).

2.3. Feedback & lessons learnt

From the organizers' point of view, Searching for common ground -events constituted a necessary step in the co-creation process. The events deepened participants' understanding of the characteristics of the "place" from the point of view of NBS design and implementation. In cases where participants gave feedback, it was mostly positive. In general, the participants found the activities well planned and guided, and the methods interesting, raising mostly positive feelings. Table 2 provides a summary of the insights from participant feedback and each LL. Especially the outdoor activities, such as sensory walks (LL Tartu), exploratory walks (LL Cagliari), and interview walks in the garden (LL Hungary) were well received. The use of simple digital visual and tools (LL Alford and Cagliari) stimulated participants' curiosity, inspiration and creativity to brainstorm jointly common activities later on. Interactive and playful mode of working in a real-life environment, sharing knowledge, wishes and values resulted in some concrete ideas to tackle and challenges that need to pay special attention in the future collaboration. The participants of all the events felt that that they had received new knowledge about the NBS, about the site and in some cases about its history. The social aspect of the event and activities was also emphasized by many participants. The events provided an opportunity to get in touch with new people, create networks for future collaboration, and they contributed to the feeling of sense of community (LL Turku and Cagliari).

There were also some more practical lessons: time is often a scarce resource in participatory activities. It is also important to reserve enough time for joint reflections after the event. On the other hand, the event cannot be too lengthy – it may become a limiting factor for participation. It was also realized that the participants in this kind of events may be very heterogenous: they may have different backgrounds and level of knowledge of the project, the NBS planned, or about the site. Importantly, they might also have different needs and expectations. In searching for common ground events

it is better to find methods that do not require any previous knowledge. It might even be beneficial to try to anticipate the perceptions, needs and expectations to ensure that none of the participants feel excluded. It is good to structure the programme so that the potential differences can be addressed. However, sometimes it is of course impossible to bring key stakeholders to the same table for organizational or logistical reasons (LL Pomáz, Catalonia). On the other hand, in some cases, and especially in the early phase of co-creation, smaller group discussions or one-to-one meetings may help build trust between participants. It might also be good to consider giving more room and active roles for the participants and taking more like a moderators' role (LL Beskydy). This may empower participants and enhance the community building around the Living Labs.

Table 2. Summary of the key insights from participant feedback.

LL	Key insights from participant feedback
LL1 Pansio -Perno	<p>Effective introduction and resources: participants found the introduction and organizers' resources sufficient for the activity, indicating good facilitation.</p> <p>Positive emotional engagement: most participants reported positive emotions like enjoyment and excitement, fostering a sense of community, though one participant dissented.</p> <p>Successful learning experience: most participants learned new things about the workshop topic and the local neighbourhood, and felt acquainted with other participants.</p> <p>High overall satisfaction: overall, participants enjoyed the workshop due to its topic, organization, and warm atmosphere.</p> <p>Improvement suggestions: adding introductory circles and involving more residents in future activities, aiming for enhanced engagement and inclusivity.</p>
LL2 Alford	<p>Positive reception: common ground activities, particularly discussing experiences and history of the park, were well received.</p> <p>Technology integration: use of the Slido app garnered good participant responses, demonstrating its potential for future presentations and enhancing participant involvement.</p> <p>Collaborative narrative building: encouraging participants to make notes on the map and contribute their own stories fostered an interactive and collaborative narrative, contributing to the collective understanding of the area.</p> <p>Engaging collaborative activity: identifying significant areas, sharing stories, and annotating the map with comments and stickers was enjoyed by participants, facilitating mutual assistance.</p> <p>Purposeful outcome: identifying favorite places and areas important for non-humans serves a dual purpose of enhancing participant engagement and contributing valuable data for the development of a virtual tour of the woodland, utilizing 360-degree cameras and audio recorders.</p> <p>Enhanced accessibility: developing a digital online access point, facilitated by the virtual tour, is seen as potentially important for vulnerable groups, widening access to the woodland and offering experiences transcending physical limitations.</p>
LL3 Cagliari	<p>Understanding activities: all participants found activities clear, coherent, and without difficulty.</p>

	<p>Emotional experience: pleasant emotions were reported, including curiosity, gratefulness, and excitement during the exploratory walk at sunset.</p> <p>Knowledge about NBS: new information about NBS was learned. People became more familiar with each other and the location. Some suggested organizing activities focused on local flora and fauna.</p> <p>Perception of activities: activities were enjoyed and facilitated idea generation, method development, and collaborative problem-solving in a friendly environment. Interaction among participants with diverse backgrounds was seen as enriching.</p> <p>Future activities: desire to implement discussed ideas, meet more frequently, and organize one-to-one meetings to explore synergies and co-create future workshops and activities.</p>
LL4 Beskydy	<p><u>Meeting 1</u></p> <p>Overall positive feedback: despite not systematically collecting feedback, the event received positive responses from participants.</p> <p>Diversity of the participants: some stakeholders were identified as conservative and may require more time and knowledge to see the benefits of engaging in activities of the LL. They are open to participation and becoming more involved in the project.</p> <p>Acknowledgment of openness: despite initial reservations, stakeholders are willing to acknowledge and potentially increase their involvement in the project over time.</p> <p><u>Meeting 2</u></p> <p>Overall positive evaluation: meeting received positive feedback from all participants, who found it inspiring.</p> <p>Active engagement: active discussions after each presentation and continued exchange afterwards.</p> <p>Specific challenges of mountain areas: mountain areas face unique challenges to be addressing.</p> <p>Recommendation for collaboration: connect activities to established information platforms, such as the Adapterra Awards, to enhance promotion and social impact.</p>
LL5 Catalonia	<p>Important encountering: it was highly important to bring citizens and the shepherds together to make the livelihood and its meaning for wildfire prevention familiar to the citizens and shepherds to get recognition for their work.</p> <p>Positive feedback from all participants: some families expressing interest in future activities. Emphasis on the value of engaging with the animals in a natural setting.</p> <p>Outdoors activity with the animals: particularly walking inside the corral, stood out as the favorite part according to the "user experience template."</p>
LL6, Tartu	<p>Positive experiences and emotions: highlighted by three out of four participants. One person expressed feelings of anxiety and concern.</p> <p>Valuing sensory walk: walk was valued and constructive ideas for enhancing its scope and impact were given.</p> <p>Suggestions for improvement: conducting the sensory walk in various locations throughout the town, extending its duration, and incorporating a more diverse range of environments.</p>
LL7, Pomáz	<p><u>Meeting 1</u></p> <p>Oral reflections instead of template</p> <p>Satisfaction with the project but time constraints.</p>

	<p>Future meetings: preference for concise, effective meetings focusing on specific, concrete questions. Need for brevity and efficiency in communication.</p> <p><u>Meeting 2</u></p> <p>Oral reflections instead of formal templates: foster initial relationship building with hospital professionals.</p> <p>Appreciation for the opportunity to discuss: expressed by hospital staff, contemplating the therapeutic potential of the garden.</p> <p>Acknowledgment of varied perceptions: among staff regarding elements in the garden, such as the presence of cats.</p> <p>Willingness from professionals to collaborate: in developing the hospital garden into healing spaces tailored for patients with diverse mental health needs.</p>
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Annex I. Living Lab reports on Searching for common ground events

LL1: Pansio-Perno, Turku, Finland

Event time and location

Time: September 20, 2023

Place: Pansio school

The place, Pansio School was selected because we wanted to have the event in the Pansio-Perno neighborhood in order to be easy to reach by the residents. The space was also suitable for a workshop because it allowed the use of different classrooms for different functions (e.g., presentations and groupwork) and small groups also have a chance to go to different rooms if they want to work in a quieter space.

Invitation:

The invitation was based on our previous work in the area and the residents' strong message that something concrete must happen and it was to plan some concrete actions that could be executed in the next couple of years. We already had a somewhat comprehensive picture of people's wishes and concerns regarding the local green areas, and the workshop was promoted to continue this work by outlining common objectives and possible actions to improve green areas.

e invited by email all people / organizations in our contact list, including City of Turku employees with relevant expertise (e.g. land use, climate, biodiversity, environment, urban planning, social inclusion, etc.), councils representing vulnerable groups, local companies, residents' associations, NGOs and those residents who had participated / been invited to the LL kick-off in April 2023. We also shared a shorter version of the invitation in the Pansio-Jyrkkälä area facebook page and in a neighborhood-based facebook group "Pansio eilen - Pansio tänään", and asked some active residents to share the invitation in their own channels. Some printed advertisements were taken to the area, e.g. to the local supermarket's message board, and a slide advertising the workshop was shown in a Film day festival event we organized in Pansio three weeks before the workshop.

Tule ideoimaan
toimenpiteitä
Pansio-Pernon
luontoalueille.

Invitation to the
event on the
webpage of
Pansio-Perno
Living Lab.

turku.fi/pansio-pernon-luontolabra/tapahtumat

Participants

Six permanent residents, mostly seniors who are active in the community. One of them was a local history enthusiast and long-term resident who was invited to give a presentation on the history of the neighborhood, and a couple participants were his friends that he had invited.

Five representatives of local companies: three from the Meyer shipyard: environmental manager who had been invited to give a presentation on recent nature acts of their company and two of her team colleagues; one from Bayer pharmaceuticals: HSE & sustainability manager of the Turku factory; one small business (a local gym entrepreneur). Seven people from the City of Turku, most working in expert positions in relevant sectors. Overall: 18 participants + 3 facilitators from the LL team.

Programme

The programme consisted of two presentations, one by the local historian and resident activist and other by the Meyer Turku Shipyard environmental manager, and a workshop where people worked in small groups to plan some actions to improve the natural and recreational values of local green areas.

The participants were divided into three groups. All groups were given a list of ideas that the residents had suggested within the last couple of years in different events and the online feedback service of the City of Turku. The resident activist also had inquired ideas and suggestions from Pansio-Perno residents in their own facebook group, and brought a number of new ideas to the workshop.

The small groups then selected three ideas they preferred and filled in a workshop template to elaborate these ideas and develop them further. Four questions were asked in the workshop template:

- How does the idea improve the current situation from the perspective of nature?
- How does the idea improve the current situation from the perspective of the residents?
- In order to accomplish / actualize, who should be involved in the execution and why?
- Where in Pansio-Perno could the idea be executed?

The results were collected in the flipcharts.

Reflections

Participants' feedback

We collected feedback surveys from 14 participants, using a scale 1-7 in the quantitative questions. The average of all responses is reported in brackets after each statement addressed here.

Experiences of the activity:

All participants agreed that the introduction to the activity was sufficient (6,1) and that the organizers' resources and skills were sufficient to facilitate the activity (6,6). The activity / method was also considered quite easy to understand (6,1) and suitable for its purpose (6,1), and the participants evaluated their own capabilities to participate as sufficient (6,3). Most of the participants found the purpose of the activity clear (6,1) and time reserved for the activity sufficient (6,0).

Emotions:

Participants reported mostly positive emotions, especially enjoyment (6,0), excitement (6,1) and curious (6,1). The sense of community was also evaluated quite high (5,5) while one participant disagreed with this statement. None of the participants reported strong negative feelings, two participants left these blank. Other feelings reported were "hopeful", "really glad about this project", and interested in learning about the viewpoints of different stakeholders.

Learning:

Most participants reported having learned new things about the topic of the workshop (5,7), Pansio-Perno neighborhood (5,9) and the local nature (5,6). A few participants disagreed, which in part might be because the neighborhood is already familiar to them (e.g. the longterm residents). Most participants also strongly agreed that they had become familiar with other participants (6,0) whereas no-one strongly disagreed with this statement.

Overall perceptions:

Participants had liked the workshop because "the topic was easy", "it was well organized and communicated", "it was interesting", "enough time had been reserved", "always something new!", "the spirit of the meeting was very warm". No-one reported any reason for not liking the workshop. To develop the activity further, one participant suggested having a brief circle of introductions in the beginning of the workshop. Also more residents were hoped to be involved in the future activities.

LL2: Murray Park, Alford, Scotland, UK

Event time and location

Event name: Exploring the diverse zones of Murray Park.

Place: Men's Shed, Alford, Scotland

Date: 6 March 2024

Time: 14h00-16h00

Men's Sheds is a worldwide network dedicated to improving well-being through the provision of recreational facilities and activities. Although Men's Sheds aim to combat social isolation in men, the venue is open to all community members. The venue provided a central place in Alford for the community to meet. Searching for a common ground event consisted of two phases.

PHASE ONE:

Participants of our previous workshop were asked to send photos of Murray Park and explain which areas were meaningful. The invitation was presented as follows:

"We invite you to share a photo of your favourite place and a brief caption explaining why it holds special meaning to you. This could be where you find solace, inspiration, or simply a spot that brings you joy. It does not have to be a professional photo, as long as it only contains part of nature in Murray Park"

Examples of photos received from the community.

PHASE TWO:

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon Europe research and innovation programme under grant agreement No101084220. Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union. Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.

The Living Lab and Murray Park users were invited to a workshop at the Men's Shed in Alford. The workshop email invitation was as follows: *"This is an invite for our upcoming meet-up next week to chat about the community activities in Murray Park. We plan to examine how Murray Park is utilised through pathways, serene spots, dog walking areas, family-friendly zones, and favourite destinations within the park. We anticipate a fun session where we will explore maps and photographs of Murray Park. Your input, your say about how people use the park, and your insights are integral to our efforts to develop a Virtual Nature photo tour for Murray Park. Your perspective will enrich our understanding and contribute significantly to the project"*

Map of Alford and Men's Shed venue proximity to Murray Park.

Men's Shed venue and meeting room in the Men's Shed with participants working with the printed map:

Participants

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The workshop was attended by four researchers from James Hutton and ten Murray Park users from the Alford community. All the participants were frequent users of Murray Park. Most had been residents of Alford and Murray Park users for over ten years. Of the ten participants, five were members of the Murray Park Trust. Representatives from the Murray Park Trust, Aberdeen Park Rangers, Murray Park woodland caretaker, retired school teacher, Murray Park Curling Club representatives, and Friends of Murray Park attended this workshop.

Programme

The group were seated around a large printed map of Murray Park (size A0 map). The participants were given stickers and pens to write and make notes on the map. The meeting started with an introduction to the COEVOLVERS projects and an explanation of how this activity would explore the use of Murray Park and their feelings about the park. They were asked to identify non-humans they have observed over the years, and by identifying their favourite parts of the park, they would contribute to building a virtual nature tool for Murray Park. Participants were asked, 'What word best describes Murray Park woodland for you?' and then used Slido app on their phones to create a word cloud.

The following exercise presented the participants with photos sent by the Murray Park community. This was to start a conversation and thought about areas of human and nature activities in the park.

A variety of different map layers were presented on the venue wall with a projector, each new map depicting various aspects of Murray Park. The following map layered zones of Murray Park were presented:

- Landmarks – Human and non-human contact
- Hydrology
- Paths and foot traffic
- Infrastructure
- Cultural significances
- Area with economic importance
- Recreation areas
- Dog walking and family-friendly areas

Different Murray Park map layers explored with the group.

Reflections

Participants feedback

Searching for common ground activities was well received. The participants enjoyed discussing their experiences at the park and delving into its history. We had good participant responses on the Slido app, which proved potential for future presentation and participant involvement (see below). Participant feedback from the Slido app during the workshop. The words increase in size as more people suggest them.

Participants were encouraged to make notes on the map and add their own stories to create an interactive and collaborative narrative, to take

ownership. The participants enjoyed a collaborative activity, helping each other identify significant areas, sharing stories and annotating the map with comments and stickers. This activity will help identify favourite places and areas important for non-humans; this will contribute to developing a virtual tour of the woodland using 360-degree cameras to capture footage and audio recorders to capture sound bites. These resources will be important to create an immersive experience that will widen access to the woodland by providing a digital online access point that is potentially important for vulnerable groups.

The different map zones on the wall provided other points of view and stimulated good discussion and involvement. This kept the conversation flowing. Some interesting discussions and themes evolved from this searching for common ground activity:

- The therapeutic potential of immersive audio for patients, including sensory stimulation and a place for emotional release.
- Creating an interactive map of interesting sounds in a specific area (e.g. gate creaking at the main park gate).
- Various entrances to Murray Park, including hidden gates and a main entrance with a picnic spot were discussed.
- The soundscape of Murray Park is sometimes filled with the sounds of children's laughter and shouting, or filled early in the morning by birds chirping.
- The wildlife in Murray Park, i.e. amphibians and insects, are more active during the breeding season. This could be an essential time for capturing footage and part of the umwelt analysis.
- Park maintenance and wood collecting.
- Wildlife sightings in open spaces.
- Nature and dog walking in Murray Park, focusing on the dogs' perspectives.
- Dogs enjoying smells in the park, not just an exercise.
- Dog owners discuss concerns about off-leash dogs in public spaces.
- Discussion about rare mushroom species, including Chaga, and commercial pickers using the park.
- Further potential to scan old photos and videos to contribute to the virtual tour and digital storytelling project.

Printed map with participant's comments and notes.

LL3: Molentargius-Saline Regional Park, Cagliari, Italy

Event time and location

The event was organised in collaboration with the representatives of Molentargius-Saline Regional Park. We held the meeting at the info point at the entrance of our LL, on 30th November 2023, at 4 pm. The location was chosen because we planned a series of activities inside Molentargius Park during a two-hour and half meeting.

Below is a map of the location, specifically marked with a red X at point "c":

We invited participants either through email, by also attaching a flyer containing a more detailed description of the project, or directly via SMS or phone calls.

We chose to conduct the activities both indoor (in a conference room) and outdoor (directly in the Park). We opted for both options to offer an enriching and dynamic experience. We wanted to have a secure place (the conference room) in case of bad

weather conditions like rain. Luckily, this was not the case but we were ready to co-create also in a complete indoor setting. The room was large enough to offer static (e.g., project presentation) and dynamic activities (e.g., dialogue in circle).

Participants

There were 21 participants with an age ranging from 40s to 60s. The majority of them were members of local associations dedicated to urban ecology, management and conservation of natural resources, or environmental and nature education. Some of them held positions as executives or teachers in educational institutions.

Programme

We structured the event into four phases. The first phase was dedicated to welcoming the participants and presenting the COEVOLVERS project (see photo 1).

Photo 1.

In the second phase, we organized an activity called "*Explorative walk*" during which participants were invited to take a walk in the park (see photos 2, 3, 4). During this walk, they were tasked with photographing scenes or specific points that evoked positive sensations in relation to a potential NBS, describing them in 1-5 words, and doing the same for those that evoked negative sensations.

Photo 2.

Photo 3.

Photo 4.

were dirtiness, impoliteness, abandonment, opportunity, neglect, carelessness, negligence, dereliction, ugliness, degradation, and anthropocentrism. There was also a brief discussion about the meaning attributed directly from participants to the chosen words. It was interesting to notice that many participants, holding a positive mindset, recognized space of improvement and opportunities even in very degraded places.

Photo 7.

The third phase was dedicated to a group discussion. Participants were arranged in a circle (see photos 8, 9) and discussed possible co-creation of ideas, interventions, and activities within the park. Participants shared several ideas to find common points with the skills of the other participants.

Photos 8 and 9.

The third phase was dedicated to a group discussion. Participants were arranged in a circle (see photos 8, 9) and discussed possible co-creation of ideas, interventions, and activities within the park. Participants shared several ideas to find common points with the skills of the other participants. Among the proposals, it may be highlighted:

- The possible collaboration between senior universities and children/young people attending schools in taking care of urban community gardens;
- Mapping of animal and plant species;
- Book corners around the Molentargius-Saline Regional Park, with the involvement of vulnerable groups (e.g., volunteers who can read books or take a walk with blind or visually impaired people);
- Cultural and musical activities (conflict between senior universities and ornithologists because of the noises that could disturb the fauna present in the area);
- Guided tours inside the Park by children from schools.

In the fourth and final phase, participants filled out the questionnaire and exchanged contact information to stay in touch with each other.

Reflections

Participants feedback

We were able to collect 11 surveys out of the 21 participants for the following reasons: some participants were not able to attend the full event, and so did not participate in the last part. The participants spent more time in the discussion part than we expected. In interpreting this event as a willingness to know more about each other and to co-create, we did not interfere with this spontaneous process.

We refer to the area investigated in the survey:

- Understanding of the activities: all participants evaluated the activities as clear, and coherent with declared aims and they did not experience difficulties.
- Emotions: all participants experienced pleasant emotions. They freely added curiosity, gratefulness for the experience, and commotion during the exploratory walk at the sight of the sunset.
- Knowledge about NBS: all participants declared that they had learned new information about NBS, and that they became more familiar with other participants and with the place. Two participants expressed the need to organize activities based specifically on local plants and animals.
- Perception of the activities: participants enjoyed the activities because they offered an occasion to develop new ideas, new methodologies, and new solutions to environmental issues and to reason together in a friendly context (the circle disposition of chairs allowed this dialogue). People with different backgrounds who knew already each other had an occasion to interact with different stimuli and this was considered an enriching factor. All participants expressed the desire to put into action the discussed ideas and to meet more frequently. They expressed the need also to organize one-to-one meetings where synergies were highlighted. They proposed to co-create future workshops and activities.

LL4: Beskydy, Czech Republic and Slovakia

Event 1

Event time and location

Event took place at the Municipal Office of Velké Karlovice – this municipality is the main entre for tourists and lies in the middle in the region (in the middle of the Beskydy Living Lab) – in February 2023.

The location: <https://www.google.com/maps?hl=sk&gl=sk&um=1&ie=UTF-8&fb=1&sa=X&ftid=0x471479cbccfd5ccf:0xdee8a504b92cc9fd>

At first we have contacted core group members and other key stakeholders via email with invitation and preliminary program of the event and later we also contacted them via phone to confirm participation and explain in person details of the event. We used our updated mailing list from previous cooperation. The advantage is that many of the invited actors already know us and it was not completely "cold" contacts. We were in email and phone contact and verifying the participation few days prior the event.

Participants

The meeting was attended by key groups of local and regional representatives such as mayors of municipalities, foresters, owners of non-profit organizations, representatives of ski resorts and local hotels, researchers and representatives of regional authorities. They represent a key stakeholders with decision-making powers whose activities affect the management of the region. In total of 16 regional stakeholders and 9 researchers from project partners (CETIP Network and IFE SAS) attended the meeting from the Slovak and Czech sides of the border. (See attached scan of the attendance sheet)

Programme

Our activities in COEVOLVERS -project are following our previous activities connected with co-creation of the Climate adaptation plan for the region with suggested measures, including NBS. So, part of the kick-off meeting was used for the reflection of these activities in relation the project's goals. The aim was to better understand specifically what the main challenges in the region from the perspective of local stakeholders are, and to start a discussion about potential and benefits of NBS.

The kick-off meeting consisted of four parts where mainly the second part was focused on the searching for common ground and we focus on that part in this report.

The first part was focused on the introduction of the whole Czech and Slovak COEVOLVERS's team as well as participants and the COEVOLVERS project was briefly introduced. In the second part Tatiana Kluvánková from IFE SAS provided input in form of a short presentation reminding the main points of Regional Climate Adaptation Plan from 2020 which was co-created together with the majority of invited stakeholder during previous Interreg project with the follow up discussion about key benefits on nature-based solutions (NBS) and main challenges related to their implementation.

With the help of a flipchart for better visualization, participants proposed possible benefits of nature-based solutions to the urgent environmental and socio-economic challenges facing the community today (see attached pictures with listed identified benefits and challenges). Participants co-created a list of potential benefits/challenges of nature-based solutions

for climate change adaptation in their region from which the water protection and management and biodiversity preservation were identified as the most valuable and needed in the region. They also affirmed their willingness to work together on water sharing and retention and the gradual conversion of spruce monocultures to a multi-species forest adapted to heat and expected water shortages. Both were previously identified in the Adaptation Plan as the most challenging climate change actions for the region.

This exercise was extremely important in relation to our common understanding and for specification of the following steps in the Living Lab Beskydy within COEVOLVERS project.

Third part focused on the presentation of the concept of the online platform "beskydyonline.eu" representing so called Virtual Commons. In this part representative of Global Change Research Institute of Czech Academy of Sciences – CzechGlobe gave a presentation of their activities in the region as well as on the impact of climate change on ecosystems and the practice of NBS in the Czech Republic. In the last part we presented details about other COEVOLVERS Living Labs and other planned activities of the project in the Beskydy region in following year. The informal discussion continued during lunch and creating the opportunity for even more discussion.

Reflections

Participants feedback

We did not systematically collect feedback from participants, however we have received overall positive feedback to the event. Although we have also identified few rather conservative stakeholders who need more time to see possible benefits of engagement in activities of the living lab. However, they are open to participate, acknowledge and become more involved in the project. Overall, we received additional feedback from many people during the lunch and most of them were very positive and wanted to discuss more, which we see as a positive finding.

Event 2

Event time and location

The event was organised by CETIP Network, SlovakGlobe (IFE SAS), and Mayor of Velké Karlovice. Event took place at the Municipal Office of Velké Karlovice – this municipality is the main entre for tourists and lies in the middle in the region – in November 2023. We are in regular contact with key actors from the region. At first we have contacted them via email and via phone to set up and fix the most suitable date. For this particular workshop we have asked core group members whether they would like to prepare a short presentation about understanding of NBS from their side. Based on that we have prepared a program of the event and circulated invitation for the event. We were in email and phone contact and verifying the participation few days prior the event.

Weather Stations in Beskydy.

Participants

Presenting participants were from:

- Slovak Environmental Agency, topic: monitoring and biodiversity of butterflies
- Lesy CR (state company Forest of the Czech Republic owning more than ½ of all forests in the country),
- Regional Directorate of Northern Moravia, topic: Water retention in the country
- Union of Regional Associations of Owners of Non-State Forests in Slovakia, topic: Agroforestry
- Global Change Research Institute – CzechGlobe (Czech Academy of Sciences), topic: Development of climate change
- SKI Bílá, topic: Sustainable development of climate-resistant landscape and tourism
- SKI Kasárne, topic: Alternative approaches to conventional agriculture
- The Morava river basin (State Enterprise) , topic: watercourse rights
- Mayor of the municipality Makov; topic: Climatic spa

Other participants represented National forest centre in Zvolen (SK) - state owned public-benefit corporation focused on forestry science, research, consulting. Mayor of municipality Velké Karlovice (CZ), Director of elementary school in Velké Karlovice (CZ), Head of the information center in Velké Karlovice

Programme

The meeting was divided into three parts.

The meeting commenced with prof. Tatiana Kluvánková from SlovakGlobe, unveiling the outcomes of interviews and a questionnaire survey conducted in August 2023. These findings highlighted the growing significance of climate protection measures and collaborative efforts in the region.

The main part of the workshop was devoted to core group members who presented their understanding and benefits of NBS. The invited professionals from the Beskydy region took the floor, presenting their experiences and examples of good practices in applying nature-based solutions to forest and water management, all within the context of adapting to climate change:

- Representative of the Slovak Environmental Agency initiated the presentations by highlighting how butterflies serve as effective and sensitive indicators of climate change.
- Representative from Forests of the Czech Republic, North Moravia, provided tangible examples of water retention in the Beskydy region's landscape and forests.
- Representative of the Union of Regional Association of Owners of Non-State Forests of Slovakia, emphasized the crucial role of local communities in enhancing environmental quality.
- Online participation included a meteorologist from the Global Change Research Institute of the Czech Academy of Sciences, who underscored negative trends in temperature and climate change.
- Representative of the Bílá Ski resort contributed insights into the implementation of water retention in the landscape and discussed community support and education.
- Representative of the Ski resort Kasárne introduced new, alternative approaches to land cultivation within regenerative agriculture.
- Representative of the Morava River Basin shared practical examples of water management implementation.
- The Mayor of Makov, who expressed a commitment to developing the concept of climatic baths.

Following the presentations, a vibrant discussion ensued, fostering the exchange of experiences regarding the implemented measures and establishing connections for future collaboration. The event ended with a joint lunch.

This opened floor for core group members to present their experience and to highlight good practice in their fields as well as main challenges they are dealing with during

implementation of the NBS was very useful for searching for common ground. Individual presenters presented their own view, but it was possible to find connections and common points in each topic. (Please see rough translation of our notes in the next page).

This approach helped initiating the discussion among individual actors and helped as to be rather moderators of the discussion. Initiating discussions, bridging actors from diverse fields, and promoting cross-border cooperation are key objectives of our Coevolvers project in LL Beskydy and this format for sharing experience among actors worked very well. It also confirmed as our previous findings that in the region any platform for coordination of activities, supporting the meetings among diversified actors and sharing ideas is missing in the region. Thus our initiative is welcomed and hopefully an online platform beskydyonline.eu based on the concept of virtual commons will help with this challenge.

It turned out that one of the key tasks in adapting the region to climate change must be education and information sharing within the local community and in relation to visitors from the region. In this direction, inviting a representative of the local primary school and also the information center to cooperate was very valuable. Although they did not present their contributions themselves, they actively participated in the discussion and closer cooperation was agreed upon in the framework of other project activities.

Reflections

Participants feedback

The meeting was evaluated in the very positive way by all the participants. They agreed that it was very inspiring which was obvious mainly during the discussions after each presentation as well as during the lunch were the exchange of experience among participants continued. Here is an example of the feedback form one participant:

“The meeting was inspiring and I wish your activity much success. Mountain areas are specific in terms of their problems and the way they are solved, and they remain a little

on the sidelines of the progress that has perhaps already been made in other areas. However, or perhaps because of this, the critical point is promotion, or if you will, enlightenment. Therefore, I recommend considering the possibility of connecting your activities to some already established information platform, from my point of view, for example, the very established Adapterra Awards, where the social impact is quite powerful” evaluated representative from the Morava River Basin

LL5: Barcelona-Baix Llobregat, Catalonia, Spain

Event time and location

The event was organised in collaboration with Collserola Natural Parc and DB Ramaders (shepherds conducting wildfire prevention grazing there).

We did our Searching for common ground -event in Can Coll, an environmental education center located in Collserola, near Barcelona (15-25 minutes by car). The building was a traditional “masia” which is a typical Catalan farm house with a different buildings for the people, animals and farm equipment. The main reason to conduct our Searching for common ground event here is because this is the place where there is one of the herds in Collserola that do fire prevention grazing, and also logistically because the place is a good venue for group activities. Another reason is the easy access for the citizens.

We invited the participants via social media (CTFC and Collserola Natural Parc channels) and through talks with different schools of some municipalities located in our LL region because the activity was also kid-friendly. At the end of the document we have added the map with the location of our LL and the Can Coll location. There is also the poster used to announce this activity.

Participants

Our target was the beneficiaries of the NBS, which are chiefly inhabitants of the municipalities where the fuel control in the Wildland-Urban Interface is conducted through controlled grazing. The most typical participant profile was a family with two adults and one or two kids. There were also couples of adults (young and seniors) without kids. Some participants came later, but in the last part of the activity (“meet the

herd”) there were 30 persons. Their main relation with the NBS was that they were visitors or citizens of the nearby municipalities.

Programme

After a short introduction speech by the responsible heads of the park in charge of the contract with shepherds, Marc and Guillem (CTFC) talked about the wildfire risk in the region and the silvopastoralism benefits in order to reduce this risk. Also, as we had some kids and park visitors, we talked about what we must do if we see the herd while we are walking, running, or cycling in the park.

Then, we moved outside, near the sheep’s place and talk with the shepherds about their job, their quotidian activities with the herd, and the relation with the environment and park visitors. After this, we divided the group in two and we entered in the corral while shepherds were talking about the newborn and other emerging questions that participants asked them. This was a beautiful moment because all the kids were so excited and happy to see and even touch the animals.

Reflections

Participants feedback

We received good feedback from all participants. Some families asked us if we planned to do this activity again. Also, most of the good feedback was related to the importance of having this herd at the park. Trough the “user experience template” the participants said that their favorite part was the outdoors activity with the animals while they could walk inside the corral. One can appreciate in the pictures the faces of all the participants enjoying during the talk and walk with shepherds. During the final part of the event we talked directly with the families to know if they were comfortable and enjoyed the event. All this feedback was very positive. Other important aspect was the feedback from the shepherds: for them it was the first time opening their herd to external visitors, and they expressed their satisfaction in showing their workplace and what they do to the urbanites. At the end, we were talking with them, and they were grateful for the opportunity. Besides what we talked about our project, NBS and wildfire risk, the activity was a good chance to promote their social recognition.

LL6: Tartu, Estonia

Event time and location

The Event was organised in collaboration with Hildegard Reimann, an ethnologist and artist. September 14th, 2023, 6 pm

We had the event in a garden in one of the districts of our LL—Kvissentali. The owner of the garden volunteered to provide her garden as the site of the event. Choosing a private garden in our LL area allowed us to engage other garden owners, who otherwise do not have access to private lands of their district and it also allowed us to raise topics that are related to urban biodiversity. We invited participants through our local LL mailing list and through Facebook groups of our LL city districts.

Participants

There were 6 participants+ organisers, the participants were both male and female, ages ranging from 30s to 50s. Some of them were residents of the area, others were garden owners from other city districts. One person was a landscape architect.

Programme

First an ethnologist conducted a guided sensory walk in the garden, where we paid attention to the use of different senses in the perception of the garden, we also paid attention to different layers of the garden (from what was above the head to what we found on the ground level) and what they offered for non-human species. We also tried to imagine, what was left out of our sensory fields, but what the other species could access. We also tasted and smelled different plants of the garden. In addition, the garden owner had set up a small photo exhibition of the insects living in her garden. We concluded with reflections on the walk, sharing experiences of inviting other species to gardens through garden design.

Reflections

Participants feedback

Four persons filled in the feedback form. Both experiences and feelings were marked positively, except for one person, who had marked by emotions, that s/he had felt anxiety and concern. One man, who was living in the same street said that he is running by the garden every day, but only now could really relate to what was there and that it was 'a meditation just 100 m away from his garden'. Probably the same participant had written in the form 'I liked the curated meditation style of guidance'. As for improvements, it was suggested that the sensory walk could be conducted in different parts of the town; it could be longer and conducted in a more variable environment.

LL7: Boldog Gellért Hospital, Pomáz–Kiskovácsi, Hungary

The events 1-3 were organised in the psychiatric hospital located in Pomáz .

Event 1

We had four meetings in the headquarter of the hospital: March 2023, May 2023 and March 2024.

Participants:

Current management of the hospital: Executive Manager (EM), Medical Director (MD) and Nursing Director (not each of them each time).

The EM started working at the hospital in the summer of 2022 and the MD from the spring of 2023, so we tried to connect to them in a period they were themselves trying to establish themselves in the institution.

These were office discussions about:

- presenting them the project and its relevance for the hospital (as this LL is a cooperation initiated by this project and with the previous hospital management),
- understanding their standpoint about the project which they “inherited” from the previous management,
- ethical issues,
- competence issues and
- practical issues.

We altogether managed to have four of these meetings resulting minutes used by the LL staff during the planning of further steps.

There were no user experience templates filled in for these meetings, we only had oral reflections. According to these, the management was happy with the project and were happy that we understood that they have no time to deal with details. They always welcomed brief and highly effective meetings, concentrating at very concrete questions.

Event 2

July 2023 – March 2024

We had these events in the hospital garden or in the building. In most cases it was the professionals who suggested meeting in the garden so that they could show us their remarks and ideas related to the current components of the hospital garden.

Participants

Mental health professionals involved in some type of therapeutical activities:

- the person responsible for the vegetable garden and connecting therapeutical activities (working for several departments)
- a care and therapeutical activities professional working at the dementia department
- art therapist working for several departments
- psychologist involved in eco-therapy

These were individual discussions.

Programme:

We either walked in the garden (transect walks) or met in a room of the hospital (interview-like situations). The aim of these site-walks and personal meetings was to provide a possibility for the medical professionals to express their experiences, opinions and needs as well as present the activities connecting to the garden they have implemented so far. We also tried to focus at some governance issues to understand the internal operations of the hospital.

There were no user experience templates filled in for these meetings, we only had oral reflections (these were the very first steps of relationship building, and we did not want to use any formal tools to not frighten our contact persons). The hospital professionals were happy to have the possibility of talking and thinking about the garden as they considered it as an important means of therapeutical work. It was also mentioned that some elements or phenomena in the garden (e.g. the number of cats) are in some ways or for some people positive, for other reasons or people it is negative, and it would be good to handle these problems. These professionals were also keen to engage in a process of cooperative thinking and acting to transform the current hospital garden into a healing garden or rather a set of smaller healing gardens created for patients with various types of mental conditions.

Event 3

We had these meetings at various departments of the hospital during November 2023 – March 2024.

Participants

The participants were invited by the head of the hospital departments.

We had two types of events with two types of participants:

1. Discussion with the professionals (incl. psychiatric doctors, psychologists, therapists) working at a certain department (we visited three departments this way)

2. Discussion with the patients (so-called “big group” meeting facilitated by the professionals of the department, two departments visited this way)

The patients at the visited departments spend 4 - 10 weeks at the hospital in general, and they get into contact with the garden depending on the department they are cured at (as each of the visited departments are located in a different building).

Programme:

Meeting professionals: at each of the three visited departments we talked about the project, its aims, framework and the experiences we had gained and activities we had implemented at the hospital. We also tried to clarify the notion of NBS and how it could be valuable and useful for the hospital. We presented the planned activities and developments and offered cooperation for everyone interested.

Meeting the patients: we presented the project frameworks very briefly and talked about the aim of transforming the garden so that it would offer more possibilities for the patients, as well. We emphasized our openness to receive ideas from the patients and listen to their needs. Some of the patients were willing to share remarks and ideas about the garden, referring to experiences and knowledge gained in or outside the hospital.

Event 4

This event was organized in downtown Pomáz in the building of the Central European University (CEU). January 2024. It was an open event.

Participants:

The participants were interested either in permaculture or in the topic of healing gardens / ecotherapy (or both). Some of them were professionals in gardening, mental health or eco-agriculture, some were autodidactic gardeners involved in permaculture.

Programme:

The event basically aimed to explore the knowledge and experience available in Hungary about therapeutical gardening, healing gardens, ecotherapy, care farming and related fields. The participants of the panel discussion (incl. Magház Association representing the COEVOLVERS project) presented their practice and related dilemmas and tried to give an overview of initiatives in today's Hungary. The event also aimed to involve the audience into a co-creative thinking process about emerging questions and dilemmas as well as the possible ways of collecting or channeling available knowledge and experience so that they can be utilized by emerging groups and organizations.

The audience showed great interest in the topic and the COEVOLVERS experience as it is unique in Hungary that a healing garden project has the possibility to cooperate with a health care institution for 4 years. We were offered the possibility of organizing a separate workshop in order to prepare a permaculture-focused development plan for the hospital garden with the involvement of permaculture experts.

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